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RELIABILITY OF WEATHER PREDICTIONS IN TROPICAL REGIONS - A CASE STUDY OF GALLE, SRI LANKA

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Accurate weather forecasting is essential for climate-sensitive sectors such as agriculture, tourism, transportation, and disaster management. In tropical regions, however, forecasting remains particularly challenging due to high atmospheric variability, complex monsoonal dynamics, and limited observational data. This study evaluates the weather prediction reliability of four widely accessible weather platforms – AccuWeather (AW), The Weather Channel (WC), WeatherBug (WB), and Google Weather (GW) – for Galle, Sri Lanka, over a six-month period (23 November 2024 – 23 May 2025). Daily forecasts with lead-times of 10 (AW, WC), 9 (WB), and 7 (GW) days were collected via web harvesting and compared against observed meteorological data using the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) metric. Using Microsoft Excel, five key parameters were analyzed: precipitation probability, relative humidity, maximum temperature, minimum temperature, and wind speed. Graphical results indicate a consistent decline in forecast accuracy with increasing lead time across all parameters. Notably, nighttime (NT) precipitation forecasts were more reliable than daytime (DT) predictions, with WC offering the most accurate estimates for precipitation probability (Average RMSE of 0-7 day lead-times for AW DT, AW NT, WC DT, WC NT, WB DT, WB NT, GW: 48, 46, 43, 42, 52, 49, 47%). Additionally, WC provided the most precise daytime forecasts for relative humidity (Average RMSE of 0-7 day lead-times for AW DT, AW NT, WC DT, WC NT, WB DT, WB NT, GW: 7, 5, 4, 8, 5, 5, 5%) and wind speed (Average RMSE of 0-7 day lead-times for AW DT, AW NT, WC DT, WC NT, WB DT, WB NT, GW: 7, 6, 4, 6, 9, 10, 5 km/h). GW outperformed other platforms in predicting both maximum (Average RMSE of 0-7 day lead-times for AW, WC, WB, GW: 2.2, 1.1, 1.4, 1 °C) and minimum (Average RMSE of 0-7 day lead-times for AW, WC, WB, GW: 1.2, 1.2, 1.7, 0.9 °C) temperatures. These findings highlight the relatively greater reliability of short-term forecasts and underscore the limitations of depending on a single platform for comprehensive weather prediction.

Keywords: Weather forecast accuracy, Tropical climate variability, Multi-platform comparison